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Application of digital technologies in accounting, business analysis and auditing

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Abstract. The intensive development of computer technology gave impetus to the beginning, and then improving auditing in the computer environment. Application of auditors by clients automated information systems needs an audit: during planning, implementation, documentation of audit work, registration audit conclusion. That is why the question seems to be so urgent automation of audit at the present stage of development.

The purpose of this work is to determine the need for the possibility of using computer technology for auditing in modern accounting.

Keywords: digital economy, accounting, auditing.

Problem solving methods. At this time, it is impossible to imagine an audit verification without the use of computers, which help auditors to solve various tasks. Among these tasks are: in information services - acceleration of processes receiving and processing information from client databases, documentary processing

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information obtained by auditors during the audit; in methodical service-development of analytical spreadsheets, creation of applied electronic audit programs, accelerating the application of audit procedures; in addressing other tasks - using the capabilities of editing texts and spreadsheets, creation of databases. However, at the same time, the client's use of computer information systems imposes requirements on the organization of the audit and selection of audit procedures, which complicates this process.

In the context of the use of new information technologies and computer techniques both during the audit and in the processing of the received statements by the auditor, significant progress is being made in the audit work. The computer becomes an auditor's tool that allows him not only to reduce the time spent on audit, but also to conduct a more detailed audit, draw up a full audit report with recommendations on strategies, directions and means of improving financial and the economic state of the enterprise.

The disadvantage of modern audit is the low level of its technology, which negatively affects the organization and conduct of the audit, the provision of audit services. In this issue, an example is large and medium-sized activities audit firms. A characteristic feature of their work is a high level of technologies. This allows the use of developed test methods that ensure fast and high-quality work performance due to efficient the use of both highly qualified personnel and numerical assistants. The main tasks of computer information systems:

1. Methodological support:
2. Information support:

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3. Technical support:

Using the capabilities of editing texts and spreadsheets (when writing the audit opinion, working papers of the auditor). In audit firms, personal computers can be used both for automation of management work, and for auditing:

1. Performing simple calculations, printing standard forms of audit documents, questionnaires, questionnaires, etc.
2. Search for normative legal acts with amendments and additions in the electronic form.
3. Obtaining information on requests to the electronic database, which generated in an automated accounting system.
4. Verification of individual calculations that are used in automated accounting system.
5. Formation of alternative forms of accounting registers and balance sheets with using an electronic database.
6. Prompt calculation of the required indicators in the process of carrying out comprehensive analysis of the financial condition of an economic entity.

To use computers in the auditor's activities, it is necessary to perform certain conditions. When conducting audit procedures using the text data method, transactions are entered into the computer system of the subject, the results obtained are compared with the certain data. The social problem of computerization of accounting is the problem layoffs of a significant number of employees, who, against the background of a fairly high unemployment is definitely a negative phenomenon in public life. Despite all the problems, computerized accounting and auditing

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systems are promising, and therefore will continue to develop. Hence, deep knowledge of computer technology and programming is an integral part of the knowledge of accounting and auditing specialists.

Scientific-based proposals and recommendations. Thus, the use of computers significantly affects control and audit procedures. However, it should be borne in mind that control functions are the most difficult functions to automate and here auditors should not separate financial accounting and auditing from oversight of information systems that generate data. Modern trends look that the future of the audit profession is not for "economic control" or "Audit" as a check of accounting reporting information, and a computer audit in a broad sense, that is, such activities will cover aspects that are closely related to statutory audit of financial statements and cover a wide range of consulting services that auditors can provide.

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